

The Impact of Hedonic Value and Utilitarian Value on Repurchase Intention Through Attitude Toward Brand:

Comparison on Tokopedia and Shopee Marketplace

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Abstract:

This research evaluates and searching for consumers' value perspective, either Hedonic or Utilitarian value, on e-commerce platform. One of the most discussed topic in e-commerce is consumer buying behavior and also post purchase behavior. Repurchase intention becomes one of the most crucial aspect as a part of consumer loyalty. Tokopedia and Shopee represents fastest growing e-commerce platform and information site in Indonesia. Currently, Tokopedia and Shopee present expansive range of products that consumers can find their needs easily. While Tokopedia is a first mover of the industry, Shopee has been proven to effectively captured consumers mind with effective marketing strategies as one of the newcomers. The purpose of this paper is to examine the repurchase intention of consumers based on their attitude toward preferred brand that consumers would choose. This also can be used for the basis and reference for owners or managers to enhance consumers repurchase intention. This research framework was developed based on the need to understand the deeper understanding of repurchase intention on Tokopedia and Shopee consumers in Surabaya, Indonesia. The design of this research is created with connecting the relationship between hedonic value, Utilitarian value, attitude toward brand, and repurchase intention. This paper used SPSS software to analyze and meaning of its regression analysis to determine and also assess the proposed hypothesis using SPSS software. Based on the survey distributed, 150 questionnaires came back with the valid data. It can explain the significance effect of Hedonic Value and Utilitarian Value on Attitude of the consumers toward the brand; and also the significance of attitude toward brand on consumers repurchase intention.

IJSB
Accepted 10 December 2020
Published 14 December 2020
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4320294

Keywords: Hedonic Value, Utilitarian Value, Attitude Toward Brand, Repurchase Intention, e-Commerce.

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Introduction

During the past decade, technological advancement and better internet connection has made business and companies boost their operations and efficiencies. E-commerce has grown tremendously and consumers are getting familiar and comfortable finding information online and also make purchases online as well. The number of online shoppers is increasing significantly, and this also impacted on the money or financial flow on internet are steadily rising (Chen, 2012). Online shopping growth in Indonesia is quite rapid, especially in recent years where the numbers of internet users has reached 17 million and the value money involved in e-commerce has reached 3.4 billion dollars. This has been considered as potential market and yet, the numbers are increasing and the trend continues to grow (Hernandez, 2003). This phenomenon is supported with the result of Deloitte Consumer Insights survey in 2019. The survey stated that Indonesia has a significant push toward online shopping experience, not only for those who seek daily needs, but also premium product. Consumers have tendencies to seek out higher quality products and it comes with greater willingness to pay premium price as well. Indonesia also showing greater demand for alternative product options, and this will give opportunities for companies to introduce a wider range of products across the entire spectrum of price, variety, quality, and options (deloitte.com, downloaded November 16, 2020).

Shopee is a Singaporean based company that provide online shopping platform for global consumers. Currently the company expanded to not just Indonesia, but also neighboring countries, such as Vietnam, the Philippines, and also Brazil. Shopee is one of the leading online marketplace or e-commerce platform in Southeast Asia. This company launched its services in 2015. The platform is designated for the region, providing consumers with fast, easy, and secure online shopping experience. (shopee.com downloaded November 16, 2020). Several studies showed the importance of consumers attitude on how they accept new technology and also shopping environment and how it affects the attitude of consumers' decision significantly (Kim, 2008). The internet is a platform of a new shopping environment and newer technology would influence consumer behavior of online shopping. Consumers would tend to search for information and share valuable information to others such as rapid delivery, price discounts, and etc. (Lee et al, 2011). Researchers have conducted so many attempts to understand the consumer behaviors toward online shopping and purchases. Consumers get what they need through provided products and services online and they are getting the utilitarian value. Many consumers claim that they are experiencing positive feelings and satisfaction from online purchases (Dholakia and Zhao, 2009).

Tokopedia is an e-commerce company which was established in 2009. Tokopedia has transformed from a platform that served online transactions, into an all in one platform of daily needs, financial and payment solutions, and also logistics and fulfillment. This company becomes a breakthrough site for companies and business to broaden their market reach. Tokopedia.com has managed to become the first internet company in Southeast Asia that has won funding trust worth US \$ 100 million or around Rp 1.2 trillion from Sequoia Capital and also Softbank. Softbank is the investor behind Alibaba's success, while Sequoia Capital is the investor behind the success of leading technology companies, such as Apple, Google, Instagram, WhatsApp, and others (<https://www.tokopedia.com/>, downloaded November 16, 2020). Tokopedia needs to address and focus on motivational factors of consumers, namely hedonic and utilitarian factors. Babin et al (2000) studied consumers online shopping, specifically on shopping activities, and the research concluded that there are two types of

consumers who perceived what they purchase based on their values. The first one is “utilitarian value” which means how consumers is trying to get the end result and more on the functionality of the products they purchase. The second one is “hedonic value” which means the value that consumers is looking for is based on their feelings and in search of satisfaction and happiness purposes. Tokopedia provides technological platform solutions and it empowers millions of partners, merchants, and consumers to participate in the future of e-commerce platform. Hence, Tokopedia have been providing variety of services to satisfy consumers with the expectation of a positive attitude of the consumers towards the brand, thus, it will have effect on repurchase intention.

Burns and Neisner (2006) suggest that cognitive and also emotional response affect the experience of online shopping. specifically referencing consumer shopping behaviors, a lot of researchers have demonstrated that individuals who has engaged in online shopping will encourage toward positive like emotions (Garg et al., 2007). Moreover, the tendency of consumer’s consumption and also purchases, especially on hedonic value oriented products and services will result in positive emotion and also happiness (Andrade, 2005). Attitude Toward Brand defines as the feelings of favorableness or not favorableness toward using the technology (Shang, 2004). Lee (2004) studied that the consumers who have tendency using hedonic shopping value as their basis of shopping will positively affects consumers’ intent to repurchase the product. Wang (2000) researched and tried to understand the phenomenon of how e-commerce is trying to facilitate the transaction of products, services and financial flows on internet. the result clearly showed that consumers with the basis of hedonic value affects the intention to repurchase, revisit, and also continue using the products. Thus, consumer with perceived hedonic value oriented will feel more on the happiness, satisfaction and also enjoyment side of return.

Fishbein & Ajzen (2005) conducted research on consumers intention on online purchases based on their attitudes. The results clearly identified that the initial attitude of consumers is based on the perspective of information-processing. This attitude refers to a tendency of a consumers use their positive or negative beliefs regarding the online purchases. The consumers reflect each and individual evaluations for specific characteristic of the matters. This resulted in tendencies, preferences, likes or dislikes over products or matters. Shang et al (2005) recommends that attitude should be an evaluation process on products, people, or matter. This can be a broad range from highly positive and accepted behavior to highly denial and negative rejection on the matter. In other words, individual consumer’s behavior toward a product, brand, or matter is something that implicates personal affective behavior. Repurchase intention is consumers’ plan in certain attitude and behavior that they will tend to purchase the products and also willing to spend money (Ajzen, 1992). There is a significant relationship between repurchase intention with the affection of brand image, therefor, companies are striving to increase brand image by any effort to advertise. The company believe that the advertisement will create stimuli, awareness, and yet capture the consumers repurchase intention behavior. Consumers who are affected and influenced by the exposed advertisement will increase their interest to the brand (Hashim & Muhammad, 2013). Moreover, consumers who repurchase the familiar brand will frequently and tend to create the resistance on brand switching. Jean Louse (2011) specifically mentioned that consumers have intention to repurchase and reuse the service provided because the consumers think that they are getting the right ratio on price-quality relation. After getting good experiences, consumers will get satisfaction on the products will tend to have a positive and favorable

attitude towards the products and also the brand, this will have an impact the intention on reuse and repurchase of the products or services. (Byoungho & Yong, 2005)

This study combines the relevant factors that would be the antecedents of consumers repurchase intention on online shopping industry. Rational and emotional state of an individuals also being discussed on this paper, namely hedonic value and utilitarian value. These two independent variable is being used to broaden the antecedents of attitude toward brand, which finally would affect repurchase intention. The result of this study will also be expected to broaden the knowledge and be a reference for future research in online shopping industries

Theoretical Basis

Hedonic Value. Hedonic value is considered one of the most important factors in determine costumer attitude toward brand. Hedonic consumers have tendencies and look for online shop, e-commerce, website and any platform that not just providing safety, interaction, privacy and any other control measure, but also, and intrinsic and exciting internet based transaction experience. This can be shown by aesthetics, sensual stimulation, and any effort to enhance the pleasure and satisfaction of shopping using internet platform. Consumers with the tendencies of hedonic values are always looking for new and different ways to get the feeling of satisfaction and pleasure in the online shopping activities (Bridges and Florsheim (2008). To et al., (2007) research result is aligned with several researchers regarding the consumers with hedonic value will feel happier, and more excited on the online shopping activities. Kim (2012) agreed with the understanding that consumers with hedonic value perspective is searching for satisfaction, happiness, and excitement on the online shopping experience, thus, the researcher used comfort and pleasure to measure the hedonic value perspective in the research.

Utilitarian Value. Utilitarian Values is defined as the value of the economic quality of a product (Park, 2004). According to Hu and Chuang (2012), consumers with tendencies and view the products based on the utilitarian value is caused solely by the perceived monetary value. Content functional attributes are tangible features of the product (Field, 2012). The functional characteristics of tangible products, such as size, dimensions, color and etc, can increase the utilitarian value perceived by consumers. Previous studies have shown that the perceived functional attribute of branded products increases their image among consumers and confirms consumers' desire to pay a reasonable premium price (Fang and Wang, 2011).

Attitude toward Brand. According to Ajzen (2008) attitude is described as a tendency to respond positively or unpleasantly to a product, object, event or even a person. As implied in this definition, attitudes have cognitive (belief, knowledge, and expectation), affective (motivational and emotional), and performance (behavior or action) components. Attitude is a perpetual state that persists for at least a short period of time and may evoke and direct a person's behavior (Eagly et.al., 1993). In Ranjbarian et.al. (2010) Attitude toward brand is as general evaluative judgment of a brand based on consumer's brand belief. According to Andrew et.al., (1981), attitude toward a brand is defined as a consumer's overall evaluation of a brand. According to Hawkins et.al., (2001) attitude has three components: cognitive, affective, and behavior. The cognitive component refers to consumer knowledge and beliefs about the brand. The more positive the consumer's attitude, the easier it is for consumers to

pick up or remember a brand. Consumer feelings or the resulting emotional reactions to a brand represent the affective component of attitudes.

Attitude Toward Brand is conceptualized as part of brand equity where brand equity is defined as the value of the brand felt by consumers which results in changes in consumer thinking about a product, for example consumer attitudes towards the brand, brand preferences and purchase decisions are strongly influenced by brand equity (Simon et.al. 1993 in Yalcin et.al., 2009). Furthermore, Chaudhuri (1999) states that attitude toward brand is the overall or sum of consumer's evaluation that they tend to do within a certain circumstance. The market share of a brand will increase when the attitude towards consumer brands becomes positive (Baldinger, 1996). Therefore, it is increasingly clear that the value of a brand is influenced by consumer attitudes towards a brand. Attitude Toward Brand is a consumer evaluating a particular brand as a whole from the worst to the best (Sutisna, 2001). Attitude Toward Brand is said to get a positive value if they are preferred, the brand is more remembered (Till et.al., 2005), and the brand is more preferred than competing brands (Hyun Seung Jin, 2003).

Repurchase intention Repurchase intention is a consumer's willingness to have tendencies or intention to repurchase the desired product in the future (Fang et al., 2011; Lin et al., 2011; Wang and Yu, 2016). Consumers' attitude in buying decision is difficult and very complex. Repurchase intention is related with attitude and behavior of consumers which based on behaviors, attitudes, and also perceptions. Repurchase behavior plays an important role in buying decision because consumers tend to consider and also evaluate any products in a given situation (Keller, 2001). Ghosh (1990) found that purchase intention as an antecedent and an effective tool in predicting the consumer's intent to repurchase intention process. Once a consumer decided to initially purchase the product or use the service of a provider, the consumer will be driven by their tendencies and intention. However, repurchase intention could be altered by the other influencing factors. Such as price and product or service quality perception (Zeithaml, 1988) and Grewalet al (1998).

The effects of Hedonic Value toward Attitude Toward Brand

The relationship of Hedonic Value on Attitude Toward Brand has been explored by so many researchers. The hedonic value on e-commerce websites often provide and emphasize on excitement oriented, entertainment functions, and any other features that would tend to attract more online shoppers. When a consumer visited a website, the features should be an important factor to significantly increase and impact perceived satisfaction and repurchasing intention (Ha and Stoel, 2012; Chen and Wells, 1999). Thus, the instrumental or hedonic value oriented factor would envision the consumer as thoughtfully considering, evaluation, and finally searching for information prior to actually purchase the product due to the enjoyment, happiness, and also excitement of the process (Babin, Dardin, and Griffin, 1994).

H1: Hedonic Value has a significant effect on Attitude Toward Brand

The effects of Utilitarian Value toward Attitude Toward Brand

The utilitarian-related websites essentially can provide consumers with their need and wants, especiall useful information and this will help decision making in online shopping (Chen et al., 2012). Consumers with utilitarian value orientation will reflect the task-orientation, while consumers with hedonic value orientation tend to be in search of personal gratification, personal satisfaction, journey of excitement and self-expression during the shopping process.

Online shopping has been proven to impact a positive feeling on shopping value perception. This will lead to increasingly positive influence on repetitive, or repurchase intention (Babin and Attaway, 2000).

H2: Utilitarian Value has a significant effect on Attitude Toward Brand

The effects of Attitude Toward Brand toward Repurchase Intention

Brand would play a huge role in buying interest and also repetitive purchases. When a consumer feels that a brand can fulfill the needs and this can leave a good impression on toward the brand and eventually, sparks an interest in repurchasing (Bearden and Teel, 1983). Repurchase intention can occur when a consumer can feel fit and in a satisfaction state on a particular brand. Hence, according to Peter and Olson (2013) belief that trust can be achieved easily and it will lead to positive brand evaluation. The market share of a brand will be increase in the attitude toward the brand consumers to be positive (Baldinger, 1996). Doods et.al., (1991) argued that the relationship between brand attitude and repurchase intention is a simple relationship which is if the attitude on the brand gets better then interest in repeat purchases will also increase.

H3: Attitude toward Brand has a significant effect on Repurchase Intention

Figure: 1 Proposed Research Model

Research Methodology

This paper is using quantitative research methods and it will include in type of causal associative research. The purpose of this paper is to develop existing and fill the gap of previous research model. To test this research hypothesis, this paper uses the basis by Sugiyono (2007) that states that causal research is carried out to analyze the causal relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Therefore, it can be concluded that causal associative research is used in this study because this study examines the influence between variables where the effect arising from one variable to another variable will create a causal relationship (causal). In this paper, questionnaires are distributed to get data of respondents and how the respondents' respond to the statements

provided. 100 Questionnaires will be distributed to Tokopedia and Shopee customers in Surabaya. After the respondents complete the questionnaire, only data that actually meets the sample characteristic criteria, will be taken for further processing. To answer each statement in the questionnaire, a Likert scale will be used from a scale of 1 to 5 in which each scale represents the answer of strongly disagree to strongly agree. After the data collected and sorted to fulfil the necessary requirements, the data will be tested to see if it can be used for this research. Validity and reliability tests will be conducted first. Validity is the accuracy or accuracy of an instrument in measuring something you want to measure. Validity test is often used to measure the accuracy of an item in a questionnaire or the scale associated whether the items on the questionnaire are appropriately used to measure what you want to measure. The testing technique used in testing validity is Bivariate Pearson Product Moment Correlation. According to Wijaya (2009), if r statistics $>$ r tables, the instrument can be declared valid. The reliability test is a study related to the degree of consistency between various measurements of a variable. Cronbach's Alpha is the method most often used to measure the reliability value of data that has been collected. According to Wijaya (2009), if the alpha coefficient $>$ 0.6 then the instrument can be declared reliable. Regression analysis is one of many methods in statistics to explain the causal relationship between one variable to another variable. Namely, from independent variables to dependent variables. The purpose of multiple regression analysis is to use the value of known independent variables to predict the value of the dependent variable. According to Hair et al. (2006), each independent variable is measured the impact by a regression analysis methods to ensure maximum predictions from a set of independent variables. Referring to the research model used, based on the regression analysis the following equation will be produced:

$$RI = b_1 \cdot ATB$$

$$ATB = b_2 \cdot HV + b_3 \cdot UV$$

Data Analysis

The questionnaires were distributed, and out of 200 questionnaires, there were 125 questionnaires returned and qualified for further processing for the first research object. This also applies for the second research objects. The respondents for the study are Tokopedia and Shopee users who resides in Surabaya, around 17-55 years old and should have purchased or conducted transactions in Tokopedia and Shopee e-commerce platform.

Table 1. Multiple Regression for Hedonic Value (HV) and Utilitarian Value (UV) on Attitude toward Brand (ATB) for Tokopedia

Model/ Variabel	R	Adj R ²	F _{sig}	Standardized Coefficient Beta	Tsig	Hypothesis
HV,UV*ATB	.597	0,356	0,000			
HV				0,292	0,000	Supported
UV				0,497	0,000	Supported

Source: Processed Data (2020)

Based on the analysis of Multiple Regression on Hedonic Value (HV), and Utilitarian Value (UV) toward Attitude Toward Brand (ATB), the R value is 0,597 This explains that there is a strong correlation between the independent variables, and dependent variables. The adjusted R square value of 0,356 indicates that Hedonic Value (HV) and Utilitarian Value (UV) are able to explain 35,6 % of Attitude Toward brand, while the remaining 64,4% is influenced by other variables not included in this research. F test results show a significance value of 0,000, and

this means that the research model is accepted. Based on table 1, we can explain the following regression equation

$$ATB = b_2 \cdot HV + b_3 \cdot UV$$

The positive coefficient indicates a direct change between the independent variable and the dependent variable. While the coefficient that is negative indicates the change is not in the direction of the independent variable with the dependent variable. From the results of t tests

that have been carried out, it can be concluded that:

1. Hedonic Value (HV) has a significant effect on Attitude Toward Brands (ATB) accepted at the level of sig. $0,000 < \text{sig. } 0,05$ on Tokopedia users
2. Utilitarian Value (UV) has a significant influence on Attitude Toward, accepted at sig. $0,000 < \text{sig. } 0,05$ on Tokopedia users

Table 2. Simple Regression of Attitude Toward Brands (ATB) on Repurchase Intention (RI)

Model/ Variabel	R	Adj R ²	F _{sig}	Standardized Coefficient Beta	Tsig	Hypothesis
ATB*RI	.432	0,186	0,000			
ATB				0,432	0,000	Supported

Source: Processed Data (2020)

Based on the Simple Regression Analysis on Attitude Toward Brand (ATB) toward Repurchase Intention (RI), the R value is 0,432. This explains that there is a strong correlation between the independent variables, and dependent variables. The adjusted R square value of 0,186 indicates that Attitude Toward Brand (ATB) is able to explain 18,6 % of Repurchase Intention (RI), while the remaining 81,4 % is influenced by other variables not included in this research. F test results show a significance value of 0,000, and this means that the research model is accepted. Based on table 1, we can explain the following regression equation

$$RI = b_1 \cdot ATB$$

The positive coefficient indicates a direct change between the independent variable and the dependent variable. While the coefficient that is negative indicates the change is not in the direction of the independent variable with the dependent variable. From the results of t tests that have been carried out, it can be concluded that Attitude Toward Brands (ATB) has a significant effect on Repurchase Intention (RI), accepted at the level of sig. $0,000 < \text{sig. } 0,05$ on Tokopedia users

Table 1. Multiple Regression for Hedonic Value (HV) and Utilitarian Value (UV) on Attitude toward Brand (ATB) for Shopee users

Model/ Variabel	R	Adj R ²	F _{sig}	Standardized Coefficient Beta	Tsig	Hypothesis
HV,UV*ATB	.848	0,718	0,000			
HV				0,156	0,000	Supported
UV				0,963	0,000	Supported

Source: Processed Data (2020)

Based on the analysis of Multiple Regression on Hedonic Value (HV), and Utilitarian Value (UV) toward Attitude Toward Brand (ATB), the R value is 0,848. This explains that there is a strong correlation between the independent variables, and dependent variables. The adjusted

R square value of 0,718 indicates that Hedonic Value (HV) and Utilitarian Value (UV) are able to explain 71,8 % of Attitude Toward brand, while the remaining 18,2 % is influenced by other variables not included in this research. F test results show a significance value of 0,000, and this means that the research model is accepted. Based on table 1, we can explain the following regression equation

$$ATB = b_2 \cdot HV + b_3 \cdot UV$$

The positive coefficient indicates a direct change between the independent variable and the dependent variable. While the coefficient that is negative indicates the change is not in the direction of the independent variable with the dependent variable. From the results of t tests

that have been carried out, it can be concluded that:

1. Hedonic Value (HV) has a significant effect on Attitude Toward Brands (ATB) accepted at the level of sig. 0,000 < sig. 0.05 on Shopee users
2. Utilitarian Value (UV) has a significant influence on Attitude Toward, accepted at sig. 0.000 < sig. 0.05 on Shopee users

Table 2. Simple Regression of Attitude Toward Brands (ATB) on Repurchase Intention (RI)

Model/ Variabel	R	Adj R ²	F _{sig}	Standardized Coefficient Beta	Tsig	Hypothesis
ATB*RI	.757	0,573	0,000			
ATB				0,757	0,000	Supported

Source: Processed Data (2020)

Based on the Simple Regression Analysis on Attitude Toward Brand (ATB) toward Repurchase Intention (RI), the R value is 0,757. This explains that there is a strong correlation between the independent variables, and dependent variables. The adjusted R square value of 0,573 indicates that Attitude Toward Brand (ATB) is able to explain 57,3 % of Repurchase Intention (RI), while the remaining 42,7 % is influenced by other variables not included in this research. F test results show a significance value of 0,000, and this means that the research model is accepted. Based on table 1, we can explain the following regression equation

$$RI = b_1 \cdot ATB$$

The positive coefficient indicates a direct change between the independent variable and the dependent variable. While the coefficient that is negative indicates the change is not in the direction of the independent variable with the dependent variable. From the results of t tests that have been carried out, it can be concluded that Attitude Toward Brands (ATB) has a significant effect on Repurchase Intention (RI), accepted at the level of sig. 0.000 < sig. 0.05 on Shopee users

Discussion

Based on the results explained, we can see that the multiple regression analysis for both research object provides an interesting explanation. The first hypothesis which this study wants to know is the significance effect of Hedonic Value (HV) toward Attitude Toward Brands, and the results has a positive and significant effect. This is consistent with the research results conducted by Ha and Stoel, 2012; Chen and Wells, 1999 which state that the Hedonic Value has been proven to increase the Attitude Toward Brand and also customer satisfaction. The Utilitarian Value consumers have tendencies to consider, search for information, thoughtfully consideration, and evaluation the product or services prior to actually commit to purchase or use the services versus the hedonic values oriented

consumers who have tendency of in search of excitement, and pure enjoyment of the online shopping activities (Babin, Dardin, and Griffin, 1994). The consumers who emphasizes on the Utilitarian Value essentially can provide and fulfil their needs and wants, especially useful information which can help decision making in online shopping (Chen et al., 2012). This is aligned with the current research where a part of Attitude Toward Brand has dimensions and factors is that consumers actually looking for useful information.

Hedonic Value plays an important role in consumer's mindsets. Brand would play a huge role in buying interest and also repetitive purchases. The Hedonic Value oriented consumers often provide focus and emphasize on the entertainment functions. When consumers visited the website, the entertainment and excitement factors was an important factor to impact perceived satisfaction and purchasing intention (Ha and Stoel, 2012; Chen and Wells, 1999). When a consumer feels that a brand can fulfill the needs and this can leave a good impression on toward the brand and eventually, sparks an interest in repurchasing (Bearden and Teel, 1983). Repurchase intention can occur when a consumer can feel fit and in a satisfaction state on a particular brand. Hence, according to Peter and Olson (2013) belief that trust can be achieved easily and it will lead to positive brand evaluation. The market share of a brand will be increase in the attitude toward the brand consumers to be positive (Baldinger, 1996). Doods et.al., (1991) argued that the relationship between brand attitude and repurchase intention is a simple relationship which is if the attitude on the brand gets better then interest in repeat purchases will also increase.

Conclusion

This model is quite simple in terms of the numbers of variables studied, but analyzing with two research objects can draw more interesting results and implications. This model is developed to increase our understanding of repurchase intention on several e-commerce platforms in Indonesia. This research model is formed from the relationship between hedonic value and utilitarian value, attitude toward brand, and also repurchase intention. Based on the data calculations and results, we can draw conclusion that the Utilitarian Value for Shopee users is higher than Tokopedia due to the company's effort to provide so many promotional and discounted strategy to lure the consumer's tendencies to shop online using shopee's platform. Thus, shopee consumers will have the utilitarian value higher which leads to their attitude toward brand finally will increase the repurchase intention. While tokopedia users are more general in their values of hedonic and utilitarian which would affect their attituded toward brand and also repurchase intention

Recommendation

Based on the result provided on the current research, there are still several limitations on the research conducted. For further research, it can be focused to complete the independent variables other that the current study. This would enhance the understanding of variables that would affect Attitude Toward Brand. Further research can broaden up the scope and broaden the respondents into different areas. This will result several interesting implications and conclusion. The goal is that further research carried out can increasingly provide deeper understanding on consumer Repurchase Intention.

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Cite this article:

Hananiel M. Gunawan & Oliandes Sondakh (2020). The Effect of Hedonic Value and Utilitarian Value on Repurchase Intention Through Attitude Toward Brand: *Comparison on Tokopedia and Shopee Marketplace*. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 4(12), 152-163. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4320294>

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